

SCIENTIFIC AND PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF SIGN LANGUAGE INTERPRETING

Absamatova Gulkhayo Bakhodirovna

(Scientific researcher of SamSIFL)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10401326>

Annotation. This article is devoted to the social situation in which a child with hearing impairment finds himself is of great importance in the emergence of his peculiarities in the development of emotions and the formation of certain personality traits. A child's personality is formed in the course of assimilating social experience, in the process of communicating with adults and peers, and is considered as a set of psychological and sociological characteristics that closely interact with each other. The surrounding social environment is revealed to him from the real position that he occupies in the system of human relations.

The development of personality and self-awareness of children with hearing impairments occurs in difficult conditions associated with difficulties in communicating with people around them, a slower process of information processing, with poorer and less varied experiences, and limited opportunities for spontaneous assimilation.

Impact of Hearing Loss

a. Functional impact

First of all, hearing loss affects a person's ability to communicate with others. Children who are deaf often experience delays in the development of spoken language.

Hearing loss and ear diseases such as otitis media can have significant adverse effects on children's academic performance. But providing opportunities for people with hearing loss to communicate allows them to participate in society on an equal basis with others. Communication can take place through spoken/written language or sign language.

b. Social and emotional impact

Limited access to services and deprived communication opportunities can have a significant impact on daily life, causing feelings of loneliness, isolation and hopelessness, especially among older people with hearing loss.

A person who is congenitally deaf and did not have the opportunity to learn sign language as a child may feel isolated from social interaction.

c. Economic Impact

In developing countries, children with hearing loss and deafness rarely receive any education. Adults who are deaf have much higher unemployment rates. Compared to the general working population, working deaf people have a higher percentage of people working in less skilled jobs. Improving access to education and vocational rehabilitation services and increasing awareness, especially among employers, of the needs of people with hearing loss can help reduce unemployment rates among this group of people.

In addition to the economic impact at the individual level, hearing loss has a significant impact on the social and economic development of individual communities and countries.

For the formation of a harmonious personality, for the development of adequate self-esteem in a child, which is necessary for establishing correct relationships with people around him, there must be a loving and understanding adult next to the child. E. Erikson considers the presence of close and emotionally rich contact with the mother in infancy as the basis for the

development of independence, self-confidence, independence and at the same time a warm, trusting attitude towards other people. During this period, the child must acquire a sense of trust in the world around him, which becomes the basis for the formation of a positive sense of self. In the future, the lack of emotional communication deprives the child of the opportunity to independently navigate the direction and nature of relationships with other people, which can lead to fear of communication.

The presence or absence of hearing impairment in parents has a great influence on family relationships. Thus, it has been established that in families where a deaf child and deaf parents develop emotional relationships close to those that are characteristic of hearing families. At the beginning of adolescence, deaf children with deaf parents exhibit approximately equal positive emotional relationships with their mother, father, and siblings. To a slightly greater extent than among hearing people, there are manifestations of negative attitudes towards individual family members. The emotional well-being of a deaf child in such a family is due, according to V. Pietrzak, to the fact that when communicating in sign language, understandable to both parties, more complete contact and mutual understanding are achieved. In contrast, hearing parents cannot communicate as successfully with their children using a small set of words and utterances that children have already learned and natural gestures.

Deaf children of primary school age and adolescence with hearing parents show fewer positive emotional expressions towards their parents than hearing children or deaf children with deaf parents; they have approximately the same number of manifestations of positive emotions towards brothers and sisters and a sharply negative emotional attitude towards their father, which amounts to their specific feature.

They have relationships with their brothers and sisters. Children openly express their feelings towards them. The relationship with the mother is emotionally impoverished, and the relationship with the father is overly saturated with negative emotions. It can be assumed that many hearing parents of deaf children do not know how to establish natural family relationships with them. Mothers probably do not sufficiently approve of their children for good deeds and are indifferent to their bad behavior. Fathers, on the contrary, strive to show a “masculine character” towards their children and instill in them the rules of good behavior, but they do this ineptly. By the end of adolescence, similarity in emotional relationships is achieved in families raising deaf and hearing children.

References:

1. Виссон Л. Синхронный перевод. – М., 1998. – 276 с.
2. Комиссаров В.Н. Современное переводоведение. – М.: ЭТС. 2001. – 413 с.
3. Комиссаров В.Н. Теория перевода. – М., 1990. – 250 с.
4. Миньяр-Белоручев Р.К. Методика обучения переводу на слух. – М.: Гардарики, 2003. – 545 с.
5. Миньяр-Белоручев Р.К. Пособие по устному переводу (Записи в последовательном переводе). – М.: Высш. шк., 1969. – 435 с.
6. Абсаматова Г. Б. LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF SIGN LANGUAGE AUTOMATIZATION //МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА. – 2022. – Т. 5. – №. 3.

7. Bakhodirovna A. G. REQUIREMENTS FOR THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF AN INTERPRETER IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS //Journal of new century innovations. – 2023. – Т. 27. – №. 2. – С. 71-74.
8. Daminov N. K., Nurullayeva S. N. THE FEATURES OF INTERPRETING AND IT'S USE //ВЕСТНИК МАГИСТРАТУРЫ. – 2022. – Т. 5. – С. 155.
9. Daminov N. K. SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION INTERPRETING AS A MODERN TYPE OF TRANSLATION //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 77-81.
10. Daminov N. Using some strategies in simultaneous interpreting process //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 381.
11. Abdimal B. THE IMPACT OF CHILDREN'S LITERATURE ON COGNITIVE AND EMOTIONAL DEVELOPMENT //Конференция: Союз Науки и Образования. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 2. – С. 46-50.
12. Abdimal o'g'li A. B. Leksik Birliklarning Lingvomadaniy Xususiyatlari ("Shum Bola" Asarining Tarjimasi Misolida) //Miasto Przyszłości. – 2023. – Т. 34. – С. 236-239.
13. Abdimal o'g'li A. B. FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLARNING LINGVOMADANIY XUSUSIYATLARI //IQRO. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 601-603.